

A Study on Emerging Trends, Methods and Criteria for Effective E-Recruitment in the Organisation

Prof. Rekha D. M¹, Naveena. N²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, ²Student

^{1,2}SJR College for Women, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

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E-Recruitment has already impacted and changed the nature of the traditional recruitment process. Availability to a massive pool of active and passive job seekers, recruiters can access and contact potential employees with a simple click of a button. Companies and recruitment agents have moved much of their recruitment process online so as to improve the speed by which candidates can be matched with live vacancies. Using database technologies, and online job advertising boards and search engines, employers can now fill posts in a fraction of the time previously possible. Using an online E-Recruitment system may potentially save the employer time as usually they can rate the E-Candidate and several persons in HR independently review E-Candidates. Recruitment agencies also use a method of e-Recruitment by using a cloud based SaaS service, there are several online offerings for ready to use recruitment software the internet, which reaches a large number of people and can get immediate feedback has become the major source of potential job candidates and well known as online recruitment or E-recruitment.

Research Methodology:

The information for this study was collected from the secondary sources. Various articles about E-Recruitment, journals and internet reference was adapted.

Literature Review:

➤ A survey conducted by Williams (2009) on E-recruitment showed dwindling recruitment spends

ABSTRACT

In recent days there is a rapid growth in the technology and it is advancing day by day. The purpose of this article is to analyse the framework of E-Recruitment. It aims at analysing the emerging recent trends in E-Recruitment and also the methods of electronic recruitment and the required criteria for effective recruitment. The major change the world is facing in the recent days is digital transformation hence this paper analyses a conceptual frame work of E-Recruitment. The organisations in the current days are adapting the technology to easier their long procedure in recruiting and the results are effective. The technological adaption in the organisation has avoided the lengthy process of earlier methods of recruitment. This study also analyses the various methods and criterion for effective E-Recruitment strategy.

KEYWORDS: E-recruitment, Internet, organisation, trends

INTRODUCTION

The world of recruitment is undergoing rapid transformation. Mass adoption of new tools and technologies has made the talent acquisition process data rich and workflow friendly. We are a part of the millennial generation, who cannot imagine life without computers or smart phones. Recruiters understand the need to be millennial friendly as that's where the raw talent lies. For the same reason, more and more organizations are now shifting their recruitment strategy to digital domain. E-Recruiting is arguably a competitive strategy that more and more companies will need to adapt in their overall business strategy and will be very important in the future.

focused on web-based recruitment at the expense of traditional methods. The author also reported that online methods proved far more popular, as two-thirds (66 per cent) of the HR professionals surveyed said that the jobs section of their own company's website was used as a recruitment tool for most jobs. Dr. A J du Plessis(2012) This article focuses on the background of the 'conventional' or 'old' way of recruiting, it reviews different 'new' ways; e-recruiting and its effectiveness; advantages such as accessibility and disadvantages such as transgression of some legislation in E-Recruiting and the impact it has on management.

➤ **Ms. D Shahila (2013)** The study helps to analyse the overall trends in E-Recruitment use and practice, e-recruitment methods, E-Recruitment Challenges and issues of E-Recruitment and its increasing scope in the recruitment process of a company. And also discuss the main success factors of e-Recruitment are the value-added services provided by the job sites, cost effectiveness, speed, providing customised solutions, helping to establish relationships with HR managers and facilitate brand building of the companies.

➤ **Dr. A J du Plessis(2012)** This article focuses on the background of the 'conventional' or 'old' way of recruiting, it reviews different 'new' ways; e-recruiting and its effectiveness; advantages such as accessibility and disadvantages such as transgression of some

legislation in e-recruiting and the impact it has on management.

- **Sills, Maureen (2014)** The purpose of this study was to explore whether the traditional recruitment process has diminished and what social media has influenced. In this paper, the author felt it appropriate to conduct a qualitative analysis along with a quantitative analysis to gain an eagle's eye into the subject. Utilising secondary research to support and argue many points made by the empirical research, the author was able to come to a conclusion regarding the hypotheses made during researching.
- **Tong, David Yoon Kin** The purpose of this paper is to examine the employed jobseekers' perceptions and behaviours of third-party e-recruitment technology adoption in Malaysia. Using the validated modified Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) without the attitude construct as the core research framework and identifying Perceived Privacy Risk (PPR), Performance Expectancy (PE), Application-Specific Self-Efficacy (ASSE), and Perceived Stress (PS) as key external variables that form the research model for the study of e-recruitment technology adoption. The results identify few key determinants to this technology adoption. Moreover, the weak evidence of the behavioural intention indicates that e-recruitment has not replaced some of the conventional recruitment methods. Third party e-recruiters' policy makers and human. The paper provides an insight for human resources practitioners on the effective use of third-party e-recruitment service provider and the strategy to attract employed jobseekers for employment.

Objectives:

1. To list out the methods and trends in E-Recruitment.
2. To outline the criteria for effective E-Recruitment.

E-Recruiting Methods:

- **Job boards:** These are the places where the employers post jobs and search for candidates. Candidates become aware of the vacancies. Special skill candidates to be searched by certain job boards
- **Employer web sites:** These sites can be of the company owned sites, or a site developed by various employers.
- **Professional websites:** These are for specific professions, skills and not general in nature. The professional associations will have their own site or society.

Trends in E-Recruitment:

1. **AI candidate screening:** Automated and machine-learning algorithms will be used to screen CVs and communicate with candidates.
2. **Jobseekers enhance their personal brand using video:** Expect jobseekers to embed video content in their LinkedIn profiles as part of building an engaging personal brand. This will offer hiring managers and recruiters a deeper insight into their expertise and potential cultural fit.
3. **Candidate experience becomes a differentiator:** Recruiting has the bad reputation that its practices are slow, outdated, and unfriendly to candidates. Organizations are starting to pay attention that a great candidate experience is an important differentiator.

Criteria for Effective E-Recruitment:

- The requirement for it is to benefit the selection procedure. Thus to make the process effective, the organizations should be concerned about various factors. Among them most important are- Return on investment (ROI) should be calculated to compare the costs and risks. It facilitates to evaluate benefits and to calculate the estimated return.
- Recruitment policy should be flexible and proactive, to adapt market changes. The companies will have their own mix and match sources according their objective. The guidelines to be provided in the policy.
- Unemployment rate, labour turnover rate are considered. As the whole process depends on the availability of candidates in the market. For every post, position it is not viable to spend too much of time. These rates will determine whether to be stringent or lenient.
- Impact of supplying compensation details to be considered. That is the wage, salary, benefits, when disclosed on line then it should follow the legal norms. Chance for negotiation will not be there. Compensation rate of the company not only reaches to the candidates but will be known to all.
- Precautions to be taken for resume screening. Words that discriminates gender, age, religion etc to be avoided and are not preferable.
- Review the results periodically and also update regularly to achieve a better result. Otherwise pool of candidates will remain static and will not serve the purpose.
- Organizations need to selective while choosing the sites. It refers to whether it is required to be giving to the job search sites like www.monster.com or in their own site. When special skill candidates are searched then generic job search sites to be avoided.

Conclusion:

Traditional methods should not be replaced by the E-Recruitment, it should supplement each other. One method should not replace the other. When two vacancies are there and two candidates are available, the companies do not have much choice, thus they prefer to widen their search and attracts numerous applications. But when for two vacancies a company receive 2000 application, the in depth screening process is not possible. While other methods like campus interview, internal search has a personal touch. But receiving application in hand, communicating with candidates becomes time consuming without internet. No doubt there has been a paradigm shift in the recruitment process by companies and the credit goes to the value, efficacy and ease of using today's career sites.

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